

Investigation of Family Resource Management for Family Sustainability in Ahmadu Bello University Community, Zaria

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Abstract

The study sought to investigate family resource management for family sustainability in Ahmadu Bello University Community, Zaria. Three objectives and one hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study employed descriptive research design. A target population comprising of students and staff of six faculties; namely Agriculture, science, education, social science, and administration were used to obtain 1098, 899, 892, 1110 and 1111 respectively to give a total number of 5149. The instrument used Likert scale to arrive at responses for the stated objectives. The instrument was tested for reliability by subjecting 25 students and staff members as pilot test with reliability index of 0.88. Data generated was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The null hypothesis involved in the study was analyzed using Chi-Square. Result revealed that respondents recognized the role of consensus building and agreements prior to decision making as a key tool for sustainable family resource management (3.27). 10 Causes of family instability regarding resource management scored above 2.50. 10 Strategies were adopted including effective use of family resources through judicious plan (3.27) and use of available resources effectively free from unnecessary expenditure, (3.21). The study concludes that resource management at whatever level requires prudent management and strategies that will utilize the available family resources for optimum benefits. Resource management can be achieved by the principles of management which should be adopted by family members. The study made recommendations based on findings that home scientists should enlighten families on resource management and family stability through mass media, workshops, and conferences. Parents should engage children in family decision making particularly in resource management.

Keywords: Family Resource Management, Family sustainability, healthy relationship family stability.

Introduction

Family is group of persons united by ties of marriage, blood, or adoption (Anyakoha, 2015). This means that a family comprises of husband, wife, children, and even extended family members. Also included are those who interact and inter-communicate with one another in their respective roles as parents, brothers, sisters and thereby create a common culture. Family is a small socialization unit that plays important roles for the survival of its members. The family plays important roles in setting goals and standard for its members, provide essential needs such as money, shelter, and food.

Family members are supported emotionally, shows love, and help to solve individual and group problems, and instill discipline. Similarly, family show responsibility for the education of its members, teach moral behavior and ensures that the family enjoys healthy relationship. The family roles also are to set and maintain a good value system and standard of living. Imogie (2011) referred to family as an institution and has affirmed that no other social institution is older and more universal than the family. Parents have the responsibility to develop the young and shape their attitude, today and in future,

families will not only need to be aware of current changes but will also need the skills in resource management to fit in the future.

Resource management is an important aspect of family living because it involves mobilization of resources towards important values and purposes, helping family members meet changing goals and concerns across life span (Anyakoha, 2015). Resources available to the family are human and economic resources and are described as major resources. Human resource requires certain things family needs to satisfy or meet her needs such as food, clothing, housing, education, health, while economic resources include money or income. Goldsmith & Goldsmith (2003) states that Resource management is the process of using family resources to meet family's needs. There are three fundamental concepts in resource management namely, values, goals and decision making. Values are principles that guide behavior, such as trust and honesty and are important and desirable as underlying motivators. Values determine goals and goals are sought after end results. Decision - making is the action taken in choosing or selecting from alternative courses of action (Anyakoha, 2015). It involves choosing between two or more alternatives. Before deciding, it is important to gather all available information and focus on steps that can help in taking the right decision (Goldsmith and Goldsmith, 2003)

Managing family resources has always been a process requiring individuals to recognize that effective decisions cannot be made quickly (Goldsmith and Goldsmith, 2003). Family resource management is a field that studies the processes of planning and using human resources toward optimal development of both the individual and family. The duty of family is to identify and communicate to other members of the family and satisfy these needs for family stability.

Family stability has been on the decline over the years (Skolnick, 2005). Many parents and children are increasingly faced with obstacles not only to material resources but also to emotional well-being. For example, children growing up in healthy,

married intact families are more likely to lead healthy and successful lives than those who have not experienced the same level of family security and stability. A stable family does not engage in activities that will generate tension internally or externally even when it involves extended family members, workplaces, or friends (Ponziatti, 2003)

Challa (2017) described stable family as family that is emotionally secured and free from overt or covert conflicts with neighbors. Milardo, Techman and Hyatt (2002) believed that family is a product of stable union between man and woman. When there is cordial relationship among subsystems of the family, there will be stability in the home. However, when the relationships are unsatisfying, there will be lack of consensus in decision on, handling finance. These result to causes of instability between spouses which will likely affect other members of the family (Nwoye, 1991). Bralton and Gold (1999) opined that family resource management unlocks the complexity of family decision making and this allows family to understand both the concepts and underlying explanation of family behavior. Anyakoha (2015) gives four inter-related steps of resource management as; planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating.

Planning is most important function of family management. It involves identifying family needs such as, shelter, clothing, food, education, health which must be met. Among these needs, priorities should be given according to their importance. Family will go ahead to identify resources available in the family and decide on those to be used in meeting identified needs. Decisions will be taken on how and when the resources will be used to meet family needs. Proper family organization according to Anyakoha, and Eluwa (2011) requires arranging activities within the plan in a logical sequence and showing the time for each of the planned activities with shared responsibilities among family members. Adequate implementation of family resource management is an aspect that enhances family stability. This is the actual process of

putting the plan into action. Implementation ensures that activities are moving on in the desired direction. At this stage the homemaker needs to supervise, monitor the activities, and make necessary adjustment in the plan be made to attain expected goal. Finally, evaluation is the last step and involves appraisal of the entire management procedure. At this stage, one checks how effectively the family resources have been used to meet family goals. Based on these steps family resource management enhances family stability being interrelated and indispensable to each order

Living sustainably according to Elliot (2014) means living within the capacity of the natural environment to support life and ensure that the current lifestyle have little impact on future generation. This study sought to find out the roles family members play for sustainable living in resource management, causes of family instability and strategies families adopt in cushioning the influence of family instability.

Statement of Problem

The family is critical in the society and when it is being threatened because of dwindling economic and social crises and challenges, the nucleus of the society then is threatened, and basic sustainable living is challenged. Nigeria is undergoing serious economic challenges, there is observable evidence of people suffering and more people living below the poverty margin. Coupled with high cost of living, which is taking a toll on the family system, the consequences are increased unemployment, food insecurity, crime, street children and children living off and on the streets. The plight of the Nigerian child has been discussed in several for a and all points to the fact that family resource management is likely to be responsible for family instability. The role of family members in managing available family resources sustainably has not been exhaustively addressed. Hence, investigation of family resource management for family sustainability in Ahmadu Bello University community, Zaria is considered for this study.

Objective of the Study

The major objective for this study is to investigate family resource management for family sustainability in Ahmadu Bello University Community, Zaria. The specific objectives are:

1. determine the roles family play for family stability in resource management in Ahmadu Bello University Community, Zaria
2. Determine causes of family instability in the management of resources in Ahmadu Bello University Community, Zaria.
3. Determine strategies adopted by families to enhance family stability in the management of resources in Ahmadu Bello University Community, Zaria.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested in this study at 0.05 level of significant

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between strategies adopted and family stability in Ahmadu Bello University Community, Zaria.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed the survey research design. Survey research is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. Result obtained from the survey is discussed in this report.

Population of the Study

The target population for this paper is the staff and students of six Faculties of Agriculture, Science, Education, Social science, and Administration. Total population of these faculties were 1098, 899, 892, 1110 and 1111 respectively, making a total study population of five thousand, one hundred and forty-nine (5,149).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

In sampling the respondents, the proportionate sampling technique using 4% of the target population was used. Therefore, the sample sizes were 44, 36, 36, 44 and 46, making a total target population of two hundred and six (206) respondents. The corresponding number to each of the target faculties were randomly selected from each of the departments.

Instrument For Data Collection and Analysis

Resource Management questionnaire (RMQ) was used, made up of four sections, consisting of a four-point rating scale items based on the objectives. Section A sought responses for personal data. Section B solicited responses on the roles played by family in sustaining family stability. Section C comprised responses on causes of family instability. Section D sought information on strategies adopted by families to enhance

stability in family resource management. The rating scale was measured as: Strongly Agreed (SD = 4), Agreed (A =3), Disagreed (D = 2), and Strongly Disagreed (SD = 1). The mean score of 2.5 is the acceptable, therefore any score less than 2.5 is unacceptable.

Data Analysis Techniques

Research questions were answered by frequency and mean computations. The cumulative means were computed and compared with a decision mean of 2.5. The hypotheses were tested with inferential statistics of Chi- square.

Results

Results of the study are presented on tables 1-4.

Table 1 showed 9 items on the roles played by the family in sustaining resource management. All nine items were above the decision mean of 2.5, indicating agreement on these roles.

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Roles Played by Family members for sustainable Stability in Resource Management

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	X	Remarks
1	All members of the family participate on decisions in resource management.	90	70	36	10	3.16	Agreed
2	Family roles and responsibility are positively executed	100	66	31	9	3.24	Agreed
3	There is satisfactory relationship between husband and wife on diverging views	98	68	19	21	3.18	Agreed
4	The needs of family members are considered on decisions concerning resource management	89	59	32	26	3.02	Agreed
5	There is even distribution of family resources, there is no rancor	88	79	26	13	3.17	Agreed
6	Family members are aware of their financial roles and these roles are done as expected	96	60	35	15	3.15	Agreed
7	All sources of family income and expenditure should be known by members of the family	86	81	22	17	3.14	Agreed
8	There is no external interference of financial management from external family members or friends	96	60	35	15	3.15	Agreed
9	Consensus and common agreement before final decision making are undertaking	102	69	24	11	3.27	Agreed

Table 2 shows that the 'Causes of family instability in the homes would be most influenced by Lack of nutrition knowledge in terms of complete dietary plans obligation' (3.27), which score was higher than the

'decision mean' of 2.5., Not economically stable to meet basic obligations (3.22), Family resource management not enough to cope with family needs (2.95). All 10 variables were above the mid-point mean of 2.50

Table 2: Mean Rating on the Causes of Family Instability in Management of Resources in the Home

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	X	Remarks
1	Inadequate income to meet family external needs	81	75	33	17	3.15	Agreed
2	Not able to judiciously use the scarce available resources among many contending demands	91	70	31	14	3.21	Agreed
3	Unexpected expenditure impacting on the scarce resources	104	62	20	20	2.98	Agreed
4	Market forces influencing on the purchasing forces on food and other essentials	99	66	23	18	3.27	Agreed
5	Insecurity and other environmental forces such as covid 19 impact	87	70	21	28	3.18	Agreed
6	No improvement in the quality of living within the family	90	60	19	37	3.04	Agreed
7	Faulty Family decision making process	100	76	16	14	2.95	Agreed
8	Not economically stable to meet basic obligations	79	71	23	33	3.22	Agreed
9	Poor communication between members at home	89	88	16	13	3.06	Agreed
10	Poor upbringing in terms of moral and character training of either spouses or even the children	91	60	33	22	3.06	Agreed

The main strategies adopted by respondent families to enhance family stability in homes in Ahmadu Bello University are presented

in Table 3. Ten strategies were presented, and all agreed as the main strategies to enhance family stability.

Table 3: Mean Rating on the Strategies Adopted by Families to Enhance Stability in Family Resource Management

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	X	Remarks
1	Strive to meet family needs through contributions of household members	70	75	33	28	2.90	Agreed
2	Identify and solve needs in order of importance	80	80	31	15	3.09	Agreed
3	Prioritize needs according to necessity	99	62	20	25	3.14	Agreed
4	Use available resources efficiently free from unnecessary expenditure	90	50	30	36	2.94	Agreed
5	Consultation with family members is important in the use of resources	83	73	21	29	3.01	Agreed
6	Use human resources to save cost (skills, talents, energy, creativity, innovation)	99	70	19	18	3.21	Agreed
7	Financial support for profitable ventures should be considered where the profit is good	96	73	20	17	3.20	Agreed
8	Share responsibilities among family members	80	65	25	36	2.91	Agreed
9	Putting plans into action through proper implementation and Evaluation	90	73	15	28	3.09	Agreed
10	Family adjustment is important where there is financial adjustment	81	71	32	22	3.02	Agreed

Test of Hypotheses

Table 4 shows the means adopted by families to enhancing family stability in resource management is significant (P<0.05). This is because the calculated chi square value of 250.349 is greater than the critical value of

55.758 at df 36 and a calculated p value of 0.011< 0.05 alpha level. This means that strategies adopted by families to enhance family stability is significant, hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 4: Chi Square Statistics on Strategies Adapted by Families to Enhancing Family Stability in Resource Management

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	df	x ² Computed	x ² Critical	p
Strategies	216 (176.6)	97 (114.2)	37 (49.1)	30 (40.1)	36	250.349	55.758	0.011

Discussion

When there is cordial relationship among subsystems of the family, there stability in the home.

Challa (2017) & Mulardo, Techman, & Hyatt. (2002) agreed that a stable family is emotionally secured from conflicts in the home and social, economic, and other external threats.

The finding on research objective two agrees with Nwoye (1991) who stated that the family is not able to judiciously use the few available resources wisely among other contending needs and this contributes to family instability in resource management. According to Anyakoha (2015) identifying family needs such as shelter, clothing, food,

education, health which must be met, is an important priority in family sustainability. Food, clothing, and shelter is the primary needs of man and other human potential resources can be tapped for the good of family life. Gronhoj (2014) stated that sustainability has been described as meeting the needs of the present without compromising ability of future generations to meet their own needs or enough for all and that sustainability involves survival and keeping the family amidst all challenges and overcoming these challenges.

From findings on the study, it could be inferred that a stable home without rancor, in which there exists satisfied relationship between husband and wife that engages in consensus building and agreements before taking final decisions, would more sustainably manage family resources to benefit the home. Also determined, is that all variables assessed that caused family instability in sustainable family resource management, adversely influenced family instability in homes

Conclusion and Recommendations

Resource management at whatever level requires prudent management and strategies that will utilize the available family resources for optimum benefits. Resource management can be achieved by the principles of management which should be adopted by family members. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Home Economists through mass media, workshops, and conferences should enlighten families on resource management to enhance family stability.
2. Government economic policy intervention should target at family stability in resource management. Once the family is economically stable, the nation becomes a haven for all.

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